

Room temperature excitonic coupling in self-assembled copper – fullerene hybrid films exposed to ambient air

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Abstract

Analytically sound combination of organic and inorganic semiconductors in designing functional hybrid nanomaterials promises new advances in nanoscience and in creation of next-generation optoelectronic devices. In this work, we report on combining two contrasting semiconductors (inorganic and organic) possessing attractive optical and electronic properties, namely Cu_2O (in form of small single-crystalline nanoparticles, NPs) and C_{60} -fullerene (as a medium supporting the NP ensemble), which were formed within the well-controlled $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films through self-assembling and ambient air exposure of the vapour-deposited Cu and C_{60} mixture. The controllability of the hybrid film nanostructure was established and verified through systematic study of the films using Rutherford backscattering spectrometry, transmission electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction, Raman spectrometry and spectroscopic ellipsometry. The remarkable coincidence of the optical absorption peaks around 3.5 eV, reported for the Wannier-Mott (WM) excitons in a Cu_2O crystal and detected for the Frenkel (F) excitons in the pristine C_{60} film, allowed us to observe room temperature polaritons as a product of the F-WM excitonic strong coupling. Quite high coupling energy of the FWM hybrid exciton estimated for the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ films in the x interval of $5 < x < 15$ (from 390 meV to 610 meV) implies the mediated effect of nanocavity photons and quantum confinement effect, strongly enhancing the hybrid exciton coupling energy. The implemented study discloses the self-assembled $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films as promising material for application in optoelectronics and nonlinear optics.

Keywords: Fullerene, Copper oxide, Hybrid nanostructure, Exciton, Resonant strong coupling.

Introduction

Impressive progress in designing functional hybrid nanomaterials as well as in comprehension of the electronic states emerging under nano-scaled structural conditions (interface, close proximity, quantum confinement, etc.) has revealed the great potential of organic-inorganic hybrids (OIHs) in advanced electronic technologies related to spintronics, photovoltaics, nanoplasmonics, and photocatalysis [1-7]. Among the numerous organic materials tested in the OIH-based devices, the fullerene molecules, C_{60} , attract huge attention due to their high stability, remarkable molecular shape and flexible electronic structure, which can be tuned, for example, by

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interaction with metals [8]. Thus, metal- C_{60} coupling in the OIHs prepared as the planar alternating layers can result in emergent magnetism at the interface that opens new prospects in spintronics [9, 10]. The use of C_{60} in spintronic OIHs is also motivated by low spin-orbit coupling and absence of hyperfine interaction in the carbon molecules that provides an exceptionally large spin-polarization length (more than hundred nanometres) even at room temperature [11]. As a result, the combination of C_{60} with magnetic metals has led to creation of the OIH-based spin valve with giant magnetoresistance [11, 12]. It is worth noting that nanoscale carbon allotropies (such as C_{60} , carbon nanotubes, graphene, graphene oxide) are currently under increasing attention due to their attractive electronic properties promising future electronic devices [13-15].

In our recent studies, we demonstrated remarkable multifunctional OIH materials with tuneable magnetic and optical properties by exploiting the self-assembly ability of a metal (Me) and C_{60} mixture [16-18]. Unlike planar OIHs, nanostructure of self-assembled hybrids is usually a uniform 3D-ensemble of small Me nanoparticles (NPs) immersed in a C_{60} -based matrix [17, 18]. It was shown in [17] that the self-assembly of the Me_xC_{60} nanostructure can be driven by adjusting Me concentration in the mixture, x . Moreover, the self-assembly atomic processes tend to form epitaxial C_{60} -Me interface promoting energy gain during such a structure organization and the Me clustering [19]. As compared with planar OIHs, fraction of interfacial atoms in the self-assembled Me_xC_{60} hybrids can vary over a wide range that implies diverse interface-driven functions of such hybrid materials.

The established principles of the Me_xC_{60} self-assembly allowed us to create the effective plasmonic OIH nanomaterials realizing proper combination of the noble metal (such as Au or Ag) and C_{60} in the respective mixtures [17, 18, 20, 21]. Analysis of plasmonic spectra of such OIH materials performed with spectroscopic ellipsometry (SE) revealed tuneable coupling between the localized surface plasmons excited at the neighbouring Au (or Ag) NPs suggesting unique applications of the Me_xC_{60} OIHs in photocatalysis [18, 21]. Detection of coupling between plasmon and C_{60} exciton in the Ag_xC_{60} hybrids implies application of the plasmonic Me_xC_{60} OIHs as the effective substrates in SERS technologies [20].

In spite of the excellent plasmonic properties of the Au- and Ag-based hybrid nanostructures, there is a reasonable tendency to use cheaper Me representatives in designing the multifunctional OIH nanomaterials, which might reveal the nanoplasmonic effects [22]. In the present study, we examined functionality of the self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} hybrids considering Cu as a popular, low-cost metal possessing excellent electrical properties (conductivity of Cu and Ag as the best conductive metals are $5.88 \times 10^5 \Omega^{-1}cm^{-1}$ and $6.21 \times 10^5 \Omega^{-1}cm^{-1}$, respectively) [23]. It is worth noting that great efforts have been spent to fabricate Cu-based hybrid nanostructures as alternative to Au and Ag in plasmonic photocatalysis [24, 25]. Nevertheless, despite some success along this way, easy oxidation of Cu under air exposure significantly suppresses the effective application of this metal in nanoplasmonics [25-29]. At the same time, evidence of the intriguing optoelectronic [30], multiferroic [31] and photochemical properties [32] of the Cu-oxides (such as CuO and Cu_2O) generates strong interest to application potential of the Cu_xO -based nanostructures. In particular, fabrication and functionalization of the Cu_xO NPs and their ensembles, especially as a part of promising nanocomposite (for instance, carbon-based nanocomposite) are the attractive topics at present [33, 34].

Considering this background and our previous results, we expected to meet oxidation of small Cu NPs formed in the self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} films. The air-promoted oxidation effects were previously observed during study of Co_xC_{60} films prepared in similar way [35, 36]. Moreover, very small size of the metal NPs usually formed in the self-assembled Me_xC_{60} films (few nanometres) suggests a possibility of complete oxidation of the Cu NPs during keeping the OIH in air [37]. Assuming the latter, we have tried to oxidize the Cu NPs possibly formed in the deposited OIH samples by keeping the samples in ambient air during one month. It was expected that such an air-treatment will result in stable OIH nanostructures including Cu-oxide NPs and C_{60} as the main OIH components, which would have attractive applications [4, 7, 25].

In contrast to the previous reports devoted to the Cu- C_{60} hybrid materials [38-41], we considered the expected oxidation effects performing systematic study of nanostructure and optical properties of the self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} samples. We found that the air-exposure-promoted oxidation strongly influences nanostructure and electronic excitations generated by light illumination. The systematic approach and careful analytical procedures allowed us to establish correlations between optical spectra and nanostructure, and to ascribe new absorption effects, detected in the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films, to strong excitonic interaction occurring at the interface of Cu-oxide NPs and C_{60} medium. Evidence of such an interaction designates self-assembled $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrids as promising nanomaterials for optoelectronics and nonlinear optics.

Experimental methods

The Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films with a thickness of about 100 nm were fabricated by simultaneous deposition of pure Cu (99.999 mass. % Cu, Mateck) and pure C_{60} (99.9 mass. % C_{60} , MER Corporation) on Si(100) substrates at the substrate temperature of 100°C in vacuum of 10^{-6} mbar. Deposition of Cu and C_{60} was carried out from different sources (electron gun and Knudsen cell, respectively) that allowed us to control precisely fractions of the depositing components by adjusting deposition rates. The deposition rates were monitored by quartz crystal microbalance. Technical details of the deposition setup are reported elsewhere [17, 18, 20]. The deposited samples were kept under ambient air at RT. Considering our former results related to nanostructure of the Me_xC_{60} hybrid films [16-18], we limited the x interval of interest in the Cu_xC_{60} films as $0 < x \leq 30$.

Chemical composition of the self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} films was verified by Rutherford backscattering spectrometry (RBS) using 2 MeV He^+ ion beam with beam current of about 1 nA and a beam spot size of 0.5 mm. The high-energy He^+ ion beam was generated by 6 MeV Tandemron accelerator (model 4130 MC, HVE). The sample was tilted from the normal ion beam incidence in order to avoid ion channeling effects in the Si(100) substrate. The properly recorded RBS spectra were analyzed using SIMNRA computer code [42].

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) experiments were carried out using a FEI Tecnai TF20 X-twin microscope operated at 200 kV. The microscope is equipped with an EDAX Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) detector. TEM images and selected-area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns were recorded by means of a Gatan UltraScan CCD camera with resolution of (2048×2048) pixels using Digital Micrograph. The SAED patterns were evaluated using the Process-Diffraction software package [43]. Samples for TEM analysis were prepared on holey-carbon coated Cu grids by brushing an ethanol-dipped grid against the substrate containing the scratched pieces of the air-exposed self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films.

X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were performed using a SmartLab SE Multipurpose Rigaku diffractometer (Rigaku Corporation, Tokyo, Japan) with $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation and a HyPix-300 2D detector. All

patterns were acquired in the parallel-grazing-incidence geometry (incidence angle $\omega=0.8$ deg.) with the detector operating in 0D mode. The incident beam was provided by a parabolic Göbel mirror and a 2.5° soller slit, meanwhile the optics for the diffracted beam were a 2.5° soller slit and a 0.5° parallel plate collimator. Data processing involved the use of X'Pert HighScore Plus software for phase identification and TOPAS V3 for Rietveld refinement.

Raman spectra of the air exposed, self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films were recorded using LabRAM HR Evaluation Raman spectrometer from HORIBA Scientific. The spectrometer is combined with confocal optical microscopy with resolution of 1 μm . The excitation of the Raman spectra was carried out by SHG Nd:YAG laser with wavelength of 532 nm. The Raman spectra of the self-assembled hybrid films were recorded under ambient conditions at RT at laser power density of $10 \text{ mW}/\text{cm}^2$.

Optical constants and absorption coefficient spectra of the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films were obtained with the high-sensitive spectroscopic ellipsometer (VASE, J.A. Woollam, Lincoln, USA) in the spectral range of 0.8–7.0 eV at two angles of incidence (65° and 70°). The ellipsometry parameters, Ψ and Δ , were measured in reflection mode. Measurements were taken under ambient conditions at RT. Data acquisition and analysis were performed using WVASE32 software supplied by producer with the spectrometer. Experimental data were fitted applying multi-oscillator spectral models.

Results

1. Verification of the hybrid film chemical composition

Figure 1 shows the selected RBS spectra recorded from the Cu_xC_{60} samples with different concentration of Cu controlled by the deposition setup (see previous section). The precise value of the metal concentration in the samples, x , shown in the plot area has been evaluated from the RBS spectra. In the self-assembled films, x defines a number of Me atoms per one C_{60} molecule [16].

Figure 1. (a) RBS experimental (dots) and simulated (fitting lines) spectra of the air-exposed Cu_xC_{60} films with different Cu concentration, x (the x values are shown in the plots). For convenience in survey of the plots, the spectra are shifted along the vertical axis. All spectra are plotted under the same scaling; however, each spectrum has different zero yield corresponding to horizontal part of the spectrum. Vertical dashed lines represent the energy position of corresponding elements at the sample surface. The spectrum of the pristine C_{60} film ($x=0$) is also shown for comparison. (b) Dependence of oxygen concentration, y , vs Cu concentration, x , in the air-exposed Cu_xC_{60} films was evaluated from the RBS spectra.

As seen in Fig. 1a, the RBS spectra include three relevant peaks nearby the energies of 500 keV, 700 keV and 1550 keV, which respectively correspond to C (or C₆₀), O and Cu constituting the deposited hybrid films. The vertical dashed lines shown in the plot indicate spectrum position of the mentioned elements at the sample surface, while the width of the detected peaks determines the film thickness. Strong edge observed nearby 1100 keV followed by the pronounced plateau extended to the lower energy range is related with the Si substrate.

The RBS spectra argue that the Cu_xC₆₀ films have been successfully created. Existence of oxygen in the deposited films can be explained as oxidation of the Cu NPs (possibly formed in the film nanostructure) during the air exposure of the samples. Indeed, oxygen was not detected in the pure C₆₀ film (see the spectrum with $x=0$, Fig. 1a), whereas introduction of Cu in the sample results in appearance of oxygen. Amount of oxygen retaining in the sample structure during the RBS experiment (i.e., height of the O-related peak) increases with increase of Cu concentration in the films, x (i.e., height of the Cu-related peak). Evidently, under the air exposure, O₂ molecules penetrate into the pure C₆₀ film through mesoporous fcc-C₆₀ crystal structure under weak van der Waals interaction with the carbon molecules [35, 36]. In the RBS high vacuum, all air molecules are rapidly desorbing from the C₆₀ sample that is confirmed by the RBS spectrum (see Fig. 1a, $x=0$). In the case of Cu_xC₆₀, the O₂ molecules adsorbed by the sample during the air exposure are chemically coupled with the Cu clusters and retained in the sample that is reflected by appearance of the O-related peak in the RBS spectrum (see Fig. 1a, $x>0$).

Consequently, the RBS spectra of the hybrid films can be described by the formula Cu_x(O_y)C₆₀ reflecting existence of oxygen in the self-assembled films introduced during their exposure to air. Simulation of the RBS spectra using SIMNRA computer code [42] allowed us to evaluate the amount of oxygen in the hybrid samples and to relate this amount with the Me concentration, x . Figure 1b shows the $y(x)$ dependence obtained by the simulation that indirectly confirms correlation between the concentrations of metal and oxygen in the hybrid films. In particular, we can expect oxidation of Cu NPs formed in the self-assembled Cu_xC₆₀ films, occurring during the air exposure. It is worth noting that we observed similar oxidation effect in the air-exposed Co_xC₆₀ films [16, 35]. In order to confirm the formation of Cu NPs in the self-assembled Cu_xC₆₀ films and the NP oxidation during the air exposure, we performed the detailed TEM analysis of the hybrid films.

2. TEM characterization of the hybrid film nanostructure

2.1. Direct evidence and description of the hybrid nanostructure.

Figure 2a shows the TEM images of the air-exposed Cu_xC₆₀ samples possessing different concentration of Cu, namely (a) $x=5.5$; (b) $x=14.7$ and (c) $x=30.0$ (see also Supplementary data, section S1). The samples have composite nanostructure consisting of the small Cu-based NPs (dark spots) uniformly distributed within the C-based matrix (grey medium around the NPs) that is consistent with our previous results related to the self-assembled Me_xC₆₀ films [17, 20, 35].

Careful analysis of the NP size distribution (one hundred NPs have been analyzed for each sample) allowed us to evaluate the average NP size (diameter), $2R$. The plots of the NP size distribution are shown in Fig. 2a*-c* below the corresponding TEM images. Figure 2d demonstrates the dependence of the NP average size, $2R$, on the Cu concentration, x . According to

the TEM results, the $2R(x)$ dependence for the Cu_xC_{60} system in the interval concentrations of $2 < x \leq 30$ is nicely described by linear function, namely $2R(x) = (3.3 + 0.11 \times x)$ nm. In the Me NP self-assembly, the increase of the Me NP size, in parallel, results in decrease of the interparticle spacing (that is the distance between nearest NPs from surface to surface), ΔL . Applying the model of the self-assembled Me_xC_{60} hybrids as the 3D-array of the equidistant Me NPs with cubic packing and with the distance between nearest NPs (from center to center), $L = 2R + \Delta L$ [17, 20], as it is shown in Fig. 2e, we can describe the nanostructure of the created Cu_xC_{60} films using the equation $L = R(x)[(4\pi/3)(1 + \beta/x)]^{1/3}$. Here, R is the average radius of the Me NPs; $\beta = n_a/n_m$, where n_a is the atomic density in fcc-Cu, and n_m is the molecular density in fcc- C_{60} [17, 21]. Figure 2f shows the variation of $2R$, L and ΔL with x increasing evaluated for the self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films using the TEM results.

Figure 2. TEM images of nanostructure of the air-exposed, self-assembled Cu_xC_{60} films at $x=5.5$ (a), $x=14.7$ (b) and $x=30.0$ (c). The NP size distributions in the films with $x=5.5$ (a*), $x=14.7$ (b*) and $x=30.0$ (c*). One hundred NPs have been analyzed. The dependence of the average NP size vs Cu concentration, x , in the Cu_xC_{60} films (d). The simplified model of the Cu_xC_{60} film nanostructure assuming ideal (cubic) packing of the identical NPs within the C_{60} -based matrix. R is the radius of the NPs; possible deviation of the NPs from ideal positions in real OIH is shown by dotted circles; L is the distance between the nearest NPs (from center to center); ΔL is the interparticle spacing (from surface to surface). Red square (cube in 3D-view) represents the basic unite of the nanostructure. (e). Dependence of $2R$, L and ΔL vs x designating the hybrid nanostructure in the Cu_xC_{60} films (f). Dependence of fraction of the interfacial C_{60} molecules, F_{in} , and volume fraction of NPs, F_{NP} , vs x in the Cu_xC_{60} films evaluated from the simplified model (g).

2.2. Phase composition of the hybrid films.

In order to confirm oxidation of the Cu NPs in the air-exposed Cu_xC_{60} films, we complete the TEM analysis by implementing the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) experiments. Figure 3 demonstrates the SAED patterns obtained from the TEM-studied hybrid films. The SAED pattern images are shown in Fig. 3a, as well as the SAED pattern plots (intensity profiles of the pattern images [43]) are shown in Fig. 3b. According to Fig. 3(a,b), the increase of x results mainly in changing the SAED pattern intensities, keeping the same positions of the detected diffraction rings (peaks). Detailed analysis of the SAED pattern plots clearly demonstrates existence of, basically, two phases in the samples, namely Cu_2O oxide (cuprous oxide) and fcc- C_{60} (fullerite), strong features of which are clearly observed at the high- and low-scattering vector intervals, respectively (see Fig. 3b). The SAED plot peaks related to the Cu_2O phase gradually increase in intensity with the x increase, while the peaks related to the C_{60} phase is decreasing. This effect is nicely consistent with variations of the Cu- and C-related peaks in the RBS spectra of the hybrid films upon the x increasing (see Fig. 1a). Indeed, the mentioned SAED and RBS effects reflect an increase of fraction of the Cu-oxide NPs in the sample upon the x increasing (see Fig. 2g), which followed by the respective decrease of the C_{60} fraction.

Remarkably that except the detection of the C_{60} -based components, the SAED patterns recorded from the $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ films reveal the Bragg diffraction features (rings or peaks) corresponding only to the Cu_2O phase. Despite the enlarged width of the Bragg peaks (related mainly to small size of the Cu_2O NPs), careful analysis of the pattern plots performed with a set of reasonable Gaussians argues that other Cu-based phases, such as fcc-Cu or CuO are not distinguished. Such an analysis of the complex part of the SAED pattern, including several intense peaks and performed for the film with $x=5.5$, is shown in Figure 3c. It is seen that except the

powerful peaks related to the diffractions from (111), (011) and (002) planes of the Cu_2O cubic phase, the complex part also includes two weak reflexes from (024) and (005) planes of fcc- C_{60} .

We have to note that the SAED patterns revealing the phase composition of the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films as coexistence of two phases, namely the C_{60} crystals and Cu_2O NPs, are nicely correlated with the XRD patterns properly recorded from the hybrid films (see Supplementary data, section S2).

Figure 3. SAED patterns recorded from the air-exposed Cu_xC_{60} films with different Cu concentration, x , prepared as the pattern image (a) and as the plot of the pattern intensity (b). Complex part of the SAED pattern plot deconvoluted using relevant Gaussians (for the film with $x=5.5$). Black dots and fitting red curve represent the experimental and simulated SAED pattern intensity, respectively (c).

2.3. Single-crystalline origin of Cu_2O nanoparticles.

The performed analysis of the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ samples argues that nanostructure of the hybrid films consists of the uniform ensemble of the Cu_2O NPs immersed into the matrix of the fcc- C_{60} crystallites. It means that the Cu NPs are completely oxidized during the air exposure of the deposited samples. The high-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) analysis does not show formation of the core/shell (Cu/ Cu_2O) structural form of the NPs in the considered x interval. Figure 4 demonstrates the typical HRTEM images of the Cu_2O NPs formed in the hybrid films. The HRTEM images clearly resolve the crystal lattice planes with the same crystallographic orientation through the particles as evidence of single-crystalline origin of the Cu_2O NPs. The interplane spacing evaluated from the HRTEM images shown in Fig. 4 was measured to be 0.25 nm. This value matches to the spacing of the densely-packed (111) planes of the Cu_2O cubic crystal, which correspond to the Cu_2O -related SAED peak with highest intensity (see Fig. 3b). This result also proves complete oxidation of the Cu NPs followed by transformation of fcc-Cu (formed during deposition) into Cu_2O phase during the air-exposure of the Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films.

Figure 4. HRTEM images of nanostructure of the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films with $x=5.5$ (a), $x=14.7$ (b) and $x=30.0$ (c). The (111) planes of the Cu_2O crystal lattice observed in the images argue single crystalline origin of the Cu_2O nanoparticles.

3. Confirmation of the hybrid film phase composition by Raman spectra

Raman spectroscopy is a very useful technique for characterization of C_{60} -based materials due to well-studied vibration spectrum of solid C_{60} . It is widely expected at present that Raman spectrum of solid C_{60} in the interval of wavenumbers (ν) below 2000 cm^{-1} includes ten Raman-active modes with symmetry of A_g (two intense modes) and H_g (eight modes with lower intensity) [8]. Figure 5a shows the Raman spectrum from pure C_{60} film recorded in the ν -interval from 100 cm^{-1} to 1900 cm^{-1} that allows one to observe the basic set of the C_{60} Raman-active modes. The modes (evidencing as the spectrum peaks) are indicated in the plot area by arrows with the respective symmetry symbols (see Fig. 5a). The number in brackets reflects numeration of the vibrational modes with particular symmetry in the Raman spectrum with increase of the wavenumber value. The most intense Raman modes, $A_g(1)$ and $A_g(2)$, correspond to the excitation of vibrations in C_{60} molecules with pure radial or pure tangential displacements of the C atoms, respectively. In the H_g -modes, the tangential component in the displacements increases with increasing the mode number. Except the C_{60} -related peaks, the Raman spectrum also includes two peaks caused by the vibrational modes excited in the Si(100) substrate supported the C_{60} film (see Experimental section). Thus, strong peak arisen at 520 cm^{-1} corresponds to the first-order transverse optical phonon mode (1TO mode) [44-46]. The second-order mode of the Si(100) TO-phonons (2TO mode) is observed in the spectrum between 930 cm^{-1} and 990 cm^{-1} as a broad peak with much lower intensity (see Fig. 5a) [45]. Appearance of the Si-related Raman modes in the spectrum argues penetration of the laser beam through the C_{60} hybrid film due to relatively low thickness of the film (about 100 nm) under parameters of the applied laser (see Experimental Section). Estimation of the laser penetration depth in the present Raman spectroscopy experiment is presented in Supplementary data (section S3). Similar conditions were applied for recording the Raman spectra of the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films, which are presented in Figures 5b and 5c. For convenience in observation and comparison, the spectra are arranged in such a way, to have the same scaling but different zero position at the vertical axis (i.e., the spectra are shifted one above other along the vertical axis with increasing x (x value is shown at the right edge of the spectrum)). The spectrum of the pure C_{60} film ($x=0$) is presented also in Figures 5b and 5c. Intensity of the C_{60}

spectrum in Fig. 5c is reduced by factor 20 in order to demonstrate the features of the hybrid film spectra under the applied scaling.

Figure 5. Raman spectra of pure C_{60} film (a) and $Cu_xO_yC_{60}$ hybrid films with different Cu content (x) recorded at low- ν (b) and high- ν (c) intervals. Raman spectra of pure C_{60} film ($x=0$) is also shown in (b) and (c) for comparison.

In order to confirm existence of the C_{60} phase and the Cu_2O oxide phase as the basic constituents of the $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ films, we have studied the Raman spectra of the films recorded in two wavenumber (ν) intervals, namely: from 50 cm^{-1} to 950 cm^{-1} (low- ν interval) and from 1300 cm^{-1} to 1750 cm^{-1} (high- ν interval) as shown in Figures 5 b, c. As follows from Fig. 5a, the low- ν interval of the spectra should include four Raman modes of C_{60} with H_g symmetry, i.e. $H_g(1)$, $H_g(2)$, $H_g(3)$ and $H_g(4)$, and one mode with A_g symmetry, i.e. $A_g(1)$. This interval also includes two mode from Si substrate (see above), which are not of our interest in present study. The high- ν interval should reveal two modes with H_g symmetry, i.e. $H_g(7)$ and $H_g(8)$, and one mode with A_g symmetry, $A_g(2)$ (see Fig. 5a and 5c).

According to Figure 5c, the pronounced peaks in the Raman spectra of the hybrid films arise nearly positions of the intense Raman modes of the pristine C_{60} film, such as $A_g(2)$ (“pentagonal pinch” mode [8]), $H_g(7)$ and $H_g(8)$ (the mode pristine positions are 1469 cm^{-1} , 1424 cm^{-1} and 1570 cm^{-1} , respectively) that confirms surviving the C_{60} molecules in the hybrid films. Nevertheless, the position of the most intense peak in the spectra of the hybrid films (indicated by green arrow, see Fig. 5c) is slightly shifted to the lower ν -values in respect to the $A_g(2)$ pristine position (indicated by red arrow). This effect, as well as the well-observed enlargement of the peak width suggest modification of the C_{60} molecules by environment in the hybrid films (see Supplementary data). In particular, formation of the Cu NPs in the Cu_xC_{60} hybrid films and further NP oxidation during air exposure can influence the C_{60} vibrational modes, which variation depends on the Cu concentration in the film, x . Indeed, the increase of x results in increase of the Cu NP size and in reduction of the interparticle spacing in the hybrid film that, respectively, reduces the volume fraction of the pristine fullerene molecules and increases the fraction of the C_{60} molecules coupled with Cu at the C_{60} -NP interface (see Fig. 2, g). The latter effects are reflected by reduction of the mode intensity and by the mentioned above shift of the $A_g(2)$ mode from 1468 cm^{-1} (in pure C_{60}) to the lower ν -values by 8 cm^{-1} suggesting transfer of $-1.3e$ charge (e is the electron charge) from Cu to each C_{60} molecule coupled with the NP surface (see Fig. 5c and Supplementary data, S3) [8]. In the hybrid films with high Cu concentration ($x=14.7$ and $x=30$), downshift of the $A_g(2)$ Raman mode increases to 11 cm^{-1} that corresponds to $-1.8e$ charge transfer to each C_{60} molecule

in such films ($6.1 \text{ cm}^{-1}/e$) [8]. The increased charging of C_{60} in the films with higher x can be explained by decrease of interparticle spacing ΔL so that the NPs are occurred to be separated only by one C_{60} monolayer (see Fig. 2f), and the C_{60} molecules of this monolayer will be coupled with two neighboring NPs. Such a double-coupling NP- C_{60} -NP will enhance negative charging of the C_{60} molecules in such hybrid films. So, the analysis of the Raman spectra in the high- ν interval nicely supports the model of the hybrid nanostructure. The estimated value of the charge transfer fairly-well coincides with the result obtained under similar experimental conditions (i.e., in ambient air) by some authors [38] and evidently smaller than that obtained by other groups using ultra-high-vacuum study of the C_{60}/Cu layer system [47, 48]. The latter inconsistency could happen because of reconstruction of the Cu- C_{60} interface caused by the oxygen adsorption and following Cu-O- C_{60} coupling, which can seriously influence charge distribution at the interface [49].

The effect of x on the C_{60} -related vibrational modes could be observed also in the low- ν interval of the Raman spectra shown in Fig. 5b. With this purpose, we magnify scaling along the vertical axis in order to increase intensity of small features of the Raman spectra emerging in this interval. The Raman spectra of the selected hybrid films modified in such a way are shown in Figure 6 (see also Supplementary data, Fig. S3-4).

Figure 6. Raman spectra of the $\text{Cu}_x\text{O}_y\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films with different Cu content (x) recorded in low- ν interval (black dots represent the experimental points; rose line is an averaging curve): a) $x=2.8$; b) $x=5.5$; c) $x=14.7$; d) $x=30.0$. The detected Raman modes are indicated by arrows: black arrows indicate C_{60} -related modes, red arrows indicate Cu_2O -related modes. The mode symmetry is written at the corresponding arrow. Strong peak of the Si(100) substrate (1TO-Si) is also denoted.

In the films with lower x ($x=5.5$ and $x=9.8$) all three C_{60} -related Raman peaks corresponding to the $A_g(1)$, $H_g(1)$ and $H_g(2)$ modes are clearly detected. However, for the film with $x=14.7$ and $x=30$, the low-frequency $H_g(2)$ mode is still seen but the $H_g(1)$ and $A_g(1)$ are seriously shaded by spectrum noise. Moreover, the C_{60} -related peaks detected within the low- ν interval tend to be shifted to the lower ν and to be broader with x increasing (these effects mainly concerns to the H_g modes) that is caused by the Cu(O)- C_{60} coupling (see also Supplementary data, section S3) [49]. We can conclude that at higher x , the Cu(O)- C_{60} interfacial coupling suppresses the non-degenerated $A_g(1)$ radial mode completely and causes splitting the 5-fold degenerated H_g modes [8, 50]. The C_{60} -related Raman modes $H_g(3)$ and $H_g(4)$ detected at 707 cm^{-1} and at 773 cm^{-1} in the hybrid film Raman spectra demonstrate much weaker sensitivity to the x variations (see Fig. 6).

Analysis of Raman spectra can receive intriguing continuation related with specification of the spectrum features, which are not covered by the C_{60} -related mode discussion. Indeed, the continuation can be certainly useful considering the film nanostructure and the phase content disclosed by the TEM and XRD results, which present the Cu_2O NPs as the second important phase in the hybrid films (see previous section and Supplementary data, sections S1 and S2). According to the references (see, for instance, [51-53]), the low- ν interval of the Raman spectra shown in Fig. 5b and Fig. 6 could include several vibrational modes of Cu_2O , some of which are Raman active, however some of which are Raman forbidden and infrared (IR) active. These circumstances are designated by selection rules for optical transitions in the Cu_2O crystal, which structural symmetry belongs to the space group O_h^4 possessing inversion symmetry [54]. In spite of the rule restriction, some real conditions (structural defects, resonant Raman conditions, etc.) can result in relaxation of the selection rules that permits to some of the symmetry-forbidden vibrational modes to be observed in the Cu_2O Raman spectra [55-58]. The conditions of the Cu_2O NP formation in the self-assembled hybrid films assume existence of structural defects generated by interface, internal stress and as O vacancies. Moreover, close proximity between energies of the Raman laser photons (2.33 eV) and the exciton of green series in Cu_2O (2.3 eV [59]) implies resonant condition of the Raman scattering experiments.

Considering our model of the hybrid film nanostructure, the increase of x results in respective increase of the NP volume fraction (F_{NP}) in the $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ films (see Fig. 2 e,g). Consequently, looking for the Cu_2O -related effects, we paid attention to the Raman spectrum features rising upon the x increasing. Except the expected C_{60} -related Raman modes, there are two new (quite broad) peaks situated nearby 300 cm^{-1} and 340 cm^{-1} , which are clearly seen in the Raman spectrum of the hybrid film with $x=14.7$ and $x=30$, which are the sample with highest content of Cu_2O (see Fig. 6 c,d). The former peak can be referred to the second order overtone of IR-active mode $2\Gamma_{15}^{(1)}$ (longitudinal-optical or LO-mode) [56], which became Raman-active under conditions of the small Cu_2O NPs (surface defects, compressive stress, possible point defects [17, 50, 60]). The latter peak can be related to the forbidden Γ_2 -mode, which becomes allowed owing to the structural defects and the resonant conditions [54, 58, 61]. Interestingly that another IR-allowed mode (TO-mode) namely $\Gamma_{15}^{(2)}$ mode is detected in the spectra of the hybrid films as a small peak nearly 620 cm^{-1} that is almost 10 cm^{-1} lower than pristine mode position [54, 56, 61] (see Fig. 6). So, detection of the IR-allowed LO (longitudinal-optical) and TO (transverse-optical) modes is caused by excitation of the LO- and TO-phonons of this mode, which become allowed

owing to the structural defects and resonance Raman effect [53-57]. Finally, we have to note also detection of the very weak peak nearly 220 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of the film with $x=30$, which could be assigned as the second order overtone of IR-allowed $2\Gamma_{12}$ - mode of Cu_2O (see Fig. 6 and Supplementary data, Fig. S3-4) [55-58]. In spite of quite weak intensity of the Cu_2O -related peaks detected in the Raman spectra (that is certainly caused by very small size of the Cu_2O NPs and by the Cu_2O NP- C_{60} interface), reproducibility of the peaks and their correspondence to the reference data designate importance of the obtained result in identification of phase composition of the $\text{Cu}_x\text{O}_y\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films.

4. Excitonic coupling in the hybrid films

Spectroscopic ellipsometry (SE) is a powerful technique enabling effective study of optical and electronic properties of semiconductors through detection of important optical characteristics of the material (optical coefficients) [62-65]. In particular, absorption and refraction of light (with angular frequency ω) in material are described by refraction index, $n(\omega)$, and extinction coefficient, $k(\omega)$, which determine dielectric function (permittivity), $\varepsilon(\omega) = \varepsilon_r(\omega) + i\varepsilon_i(\omega)$, and absorption coefficient, $\alpha(\omega)$, as following [66]

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_r &= n^2 - k^2, \\ \varepsilon_i &= 2nk, \\ \alpha(\omega) &= 4\pi k(\omega)/\lambda.\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

In the equations (1), $\varepsilon_r(\omega)$ and $\varepsilon_i(\omega)$ are real and imaginary parts of the complex dielectric function, $\varepsilon(\omega)$, respectively; λ is the light wavelength. The real (dispersive) and imaginary (absorptive) parts of ε describe, respectively, the polarization efficiency under electric field of the illuminating light and the energy losses caused by electronic transitions [55]. Trying to detect the effect of Cu_2O NPs on electronic transitions in C_{60} , we performed systematic analysis of absorption coefficient spectra of the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films, considering the relation between ε_i and α in (1).

First of all, we have to stress a great significance of the Cu_2O oxide as a promising semiconductor, which remarkable optical and electronic properties imply effective applications of this material in catalysis, photovoltaics and nonlinear optics [67-70]. The most exciting effect of Cu_2O electronic structure on light illumination is the excitation of Rydberg series of excitons detected at low temperature in different wavelength intervals. Thus, study of absorption spectra in visible light wavelengths revealed existence of several excitonic series, namely yellow, green, blue and indigo exciton series (see section S4 in Supplementary data and [71-74]). The mentioned electronic transitions at the Γ -point of Brillouin zone generating these excitation series are demonstrated in Supplementary data (see Fig. S5-1a). Thus, the transitions related to the yellow series designate lowest Cu_2O band gap estimated as 2.17 eV [61, 74, 75]. Despite that the increased temperature results in strong suppression of the exciton-induced absorption, the accurate preparation of the bulk Cu_2O samples allowed some authors to observed the absorption effects from blue (at 2.64 eV) and indigo (at 2.76 eV) Γ -excitons even at RT through study of the $\varepsilon(\omega)$

spectra recorded with spectroscopic ellipsometry [76]. They also report on detection of strong absorption peaks nearly 3.5 eV (E_{1A} peak) and nearly 4.3 eV (E_{1B} peak), which were ascribed to 2D discrete excitons, excited respectively at the X- and M-points of Brillouin zone [75-77]. The latter results and our knowledge on the C_{60} absorption spectrum [20, 21, 50] allowed us to suspect possible resonant interactions of the excitations taken place in C_{60} and Cu_2O at the interfaces of the hybrid films. These expectations motivated us to investigate rigorously the optical effects generated by the Cu_2O and C_{60} under conditions of the $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ hybrid films using the high-sensitive SE technique.

Figure 7 shows the spectra of dielectric constants of the pure C_{60} film (Fig. 7 a) and the selected $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ hybrid films (Fig. 7 b,c) recorded at RT by means of SE. As seen from Fig. 7a, the ϵ_i spectrum of pure C_{60} film reveals several peaks situated quite close to the energetic positions of the absorption peaks detected in Cu_2O crystal by Ito *et al* [76]. The evident similarity of the optical spectra of C_{60} and Cu_2O claims us to analyze carefully the absorption spectra from the $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ hybrids in order to look for a possible interaction between the C_{60} excitons [78, 79] and the Cu_2O excitons [72, 74] at the organic-inorganic interfaces. To perform the relevant analysis, we converted the $\epsilon(E)$ spectra into the spectra of the absorption coefficient, $\alpha(E)$, using the equations (1). Here, E is the incident photon energy.

Figure 7. Optical spectra of real ϵ_r (blue curves) and imaginary ϵ_i (red curves) parts of the dielectric function $\epsilon(E)$ recorded from pure C_{60} film (a) and from selected $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ hybrid films with $x=5.5$ (b) and $x=14.7$ (c).

Figure 8 demonstrates the $\alpha(E)$ optical spectra recorded for the pure C_{60} film ($x=0$) and for the selected $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ hybrid films. As seen, the $\alpha(E)$ spectra of the hybrid films do not show the plasmon-related absorption peak, which is expected to arise in the energy interval of 1.5 – 2.2 eV [26, 29, 80-82]. In fact, absence of the plasmonic peak also argues the complete oxidation of the Cu NPs in the hybrid films. Comparison of the spectra allows us to deduce two main tendencies in the spectra variations with x increasing. Firstly, there is a gradual decrease of the C_{60} -related absorption peaks that can be ascribed to reduction of fraction of the pristine C_{60} molecules in the hybrid with higher x (see Section 2 and Fig. 2g) [18, 21]. Secondly, the increase of x results in the well-resolved shift of the absorption peak observed nearly 3 eV (indicated by arrow in Fig. 8) to the lower E that implies activation of new electronic transitions.

Figure 8. Experimental spectra of absorption coefficient, $\alpha(E)$, recorded by means of SE from pure C_{60} (in blue) and $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ hybrid films with different x (see inset). Additional peak appeared in the hybrid film spectra around 3 eV is indicated by arrows.

In order to specify these electronic transitions, the absorption spectra have been analyzed using the Lorentz-oscillators' model, which was found to be rather useful in identification of the main absorption peaks in the Me_xC_{60} optical spectra as the resonant excitation of the appropriate Lorentz oscillators [18, 21, 50]. Considering this model, we describe optical absorption of the hybrid film, $\alpha(\omega)$, as superposition of N Lorentzians corresponding to N types of the electronic oscillators with own frequency ω_j , oscillator strength f_j and dumping coefficient γ_j , namely [83]

$$\alpha(\omega) = \sum_j \frac{f_j}{(\omega_j^2 - \omega^2) - i\gamma_j\omega} \quad (2)$$

The analysis of the absorption coefficient (AC) spectra using this model and the equation (2) are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Absorption coefficient (AC) spectra of pure C_{60} and $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ hybrid films with different x recorded by SE at RT. The AC spectra are deconvoluted using appropriate Lorentzians corresponding to the respective electronic excitations. Superposition of Lorentzians is shown by red curve fitting the experimental spectra (black dots). The Lorentz peaks under discussion are shown in color (see the text).

Figure 9a shows application of the Lorentz model for analysis of the AC spectra recorded from pure C_{60} film. The spectrum features (i.e. peaks and bends) allow us to apply set of the appropriate Lorentzians to obtain precise coincidence between the simulated spectrum (red curve) prepared by the Lorentzian superposition and the experimental SE spectrum (black dots). The evaluated Lorentzians correspond to the allowed electronic transitions in the pristine C_{60} film induced by the incident light, namely $h_u \rightarrow t_{1g}$ (peak A, 2.73 eV), $h_g + g_g \rightarrow t_{1u}$ (peak B, 3.55 eV), $h_u \rightarrow h_g$ (peak C, 4.67 eV), and $g_g + h_g \rightarrow t_{2u}$ (peak D, 5.65 eV) [8, 50] (see also Supplementary data, Fig. S4-1c). The analysis also revealed the high-energy AC peak (peak E, nearby 6.2 eV) reported in other references [8, 18, 21].

Discussion

The performed analysis of the AC spectrum recorded from pure C_{60} films evidences that the energy of some C_{60} -related peaks is very close to that detected in the Cu_2O crystal by the Ito *et al* [76]. As for the $Cu_x(O_y)C_{60}$ hybrid films, the energetic and spatial proximity of the electronic excitations taken place at the C_{60} and Cu_2O interface should result in quantum-mechanical mixing of the resonant states followed by the energy level splitting and by formation of the stable hybrid exciton [4, 84, 85]. The latter circumstances allowed us to expect specific modification of the AC spectrum of the hybrid film as compared with one recorded from the pure C_{60} film. Indeed, new features in the AC spectrum of the hybrid film appear around the energy of 3.5 eV (i.e. around the C_{60} -related B-peak). In particular, the double peak is surely detected in the AC spectra of the films with $x > 5$ (see Fig. 8 and Fig. 9c-e), which are the films with relatively high fraction of the Cu_2O NPs, namely with $F_{NP} > 0.1$ (see Figs. 2d). According to the Lorentz-oscillators' model analysis, these features can be evaluated as two absorption peaks (the colored Lorentzians indicated by black arrows in Fig. 8 c-e) situated in close vicinity of the position of the B-peak detected in the AC spectrum of the pure C_{60} film (see Fig. 9). Considering the above-mentioned correlations between the excitations detected in pure C_{60} (see Fig. 8a) and in pure Cu_2O [76], we can ascribe these two Lorentzians to the product of the resonant hybridization between the C_{60} exciton (Frenkel-type exciton [78, 79]) and the Cu_2O exciton (Wannier-Mott-type exciton [84, 85]) occurring at the interface of the hybrid film (see also Supplementary data, Fig. S4-1 b,c). Such an excitonic interaction results in creation of the Frenkel-Wannier-Mott (FWM) hybrid exciton [4, 86]. Indeed,

quantum mechanical simulations of the resonant F-WM excitonic interaction nicely explains these two peaks found in the AC spectrum of the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ film as splitting of the mixed degenerated states of the FWM hybrid exciton formed in strong coupling regime [4]. Access to the strong excitonic coupling is provided by sufficiently high coupling energy of the hybridized excitons, which can be roughly estimated as the energy interval between the states of the hybrid exciton [4, 86]. The simplified diagram of the hybrid FWM-exciton formation under the incident photons with energy $E_0 = \hbar\omega_0$ (\hbar is Plank constant, ω_0 is the photon frequency) is shown in Figure 10a. The corresponding results related to the hybrid exciton coupling energy are shown in Fig. 10b. Coupling energy, ΔE , was evaluated as the energy interval between the respective Lorentz peaks in the AC spectra of the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ films (see Fig. 9).

Figure 10. (a) Energetic diagram illustrating resonant coupling of C_{60} F- and Cu_2O NP WM-excitons followed by formation of stable hybrid FWM-exciton. (b) Dependence of the UP and LP exciton-polaritons (relevant AC peak positions) and the estimated F-WM exciton coupling energy, ΔE , on Cu concentration, x . (c) Dependence of the F-WM exciton coupling energy, ΔE , on spacing between the Cu_2O nanoparticles, ΔL , in the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films.

Theoretical models of the F-WM excitonic strong coupling yield the value of coupling energy (order of 10 meV) that is almost one order of magnitude lower than the values evaluated from the experimental AC spectra (see Fig. 10b) [4]. Such a circumstance claims us to consider possible mechanisms of enhancement of the F-WM exciton coupling strength.

One mechanism would concern to the concept of optical cavity. Indeed, the F-WM exciton coupling energy can be much higher, if the excitonic interaction is mediated by the cavity photons [4, 87, 88]. In the presented $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ films, role of cavity could play a small nanosized volume confined between the neighboring Cu_2O NPs (so-called, “nanocavity” [89]), while the relevant nanocavity photons are emitted through annihilation of the WM excitons. The nanocavity configuration provides strong interaction between the excitons and the photons that would be explained as creation of new quasiparticles (polaritons) [4, 90, 91]. Dispersion function of the cavity photon-FWM hybrid exciton represents two branches (upper-branch polariton, UP and lower-branch polariton, LP) avoiding crossing at the resonance frequency [4]. Such an anti-crossing behavior of the polaritons is known as Rabi splitting effect, while the energy gap at the resonance defines a Rabi splitting energy, which reflects coupling strength of the exciton-polaritons [4]. Thus, in organic microcavity, the values of the Rabi splitting energy at RT was reported to be 100-450 meV [4, 92, 93] that is in qualitative agreement with our estimations executed for the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films. Using the concept of nanocavity, we can relate the

detected low- and high-energy AC-peaks of the FWM hybrid exciton to the LP and UP, respectively. In such a case, Figure 10b (bottom plot) represents the resonant LP and UP levels in the considered interval of x (from 5.5 to 14.7), as well as the Figure 10b (top plot) shows the shows the F-WM exciton coupling energy, which varies from 390 meV to 610 meV.

Another reason of the F-WM exciton coupling strength enhancement could be related to the quantum confinement effect. As show some reports, spatial confinement of the exciton in semiconducting nanostructure (quantum dots, wells or wires, core-shell NPs, interfaces, etc.) can strongly influences properties of the quasiparticle (namely, binding energy, bandgap, energy spectrum) that consequently changes the optical and electrical properties of the material [94-97]. As a result, quantum confinement can strongly affect the interaction of the exciton with other quasiparticles. In particular, the confinement effect was reported for interaction of exciton with exciton [98], exciton with phonon [99], and exciton with polariton [100]. As for the $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films, the quantum confinement effect of the F-WM interaction is nicely observed in Fig. 10c, which shows the dependence of coupling energy, ΔE , on interparticle spacing, ΔL , evaluated with our model of the hybrid material (see Fig. 2). As could be seen, the coupling energy magnitude reveals exponential growth, when ΔL decreases from 3.6 nm up to 2.5 nm.

Considering the presented argumentation, the details of the hybrid film nanostructure and some reports (for instance, [100]), we suspect contribution of both mechanisms (i.e., nanocavity and quantum confinement) in the exciton coupling enhancement evaluated for the studied $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films that results in quite stable FWM hybrid exciton existing even at RT.

It is worth noting that significant increase of Cu concentration in the hybrid film up to $x=30$, however, strongly suppresses the excitonic coupling due to quite small interparticle spacing (ΔL is order of 1 nm, see Fig. 2f and Fig. 9f). In such a film nanostructure, large number of the C_{60} molecules will be affected by internal stress and chemical bonding with the Cu_2O NPs [16, 17] that is reflected, in particular, by global decrease of the absorption intensity along the whole energy interval of the AC spectrum (see Fig. 9f). Moreover, at such high concentrations of metal in the Me_xC_{60} mixture, the self-assembly of nanostructure is followed by coalescence of the Me NPs and decomposition of C_{60} molecules (see Supplementary data, section S3) leading to degradation of the hybrid film properties [16, 17], in particular, to worsening F-MW excitonic coupling effect.

Conclusion

We report on creation and systematic analysis of the organic-inorganic $\text{Cu}_x(\text{O}_y)\text{C}_{60}$ hybrid films with well-controlled composite nanostructure consisting of the Cu_2O single-crystalline NPs. Such a remarkable hybrid nanostructure of the films was formed through self-assembling the depositing Cu and C_{60} mixture and post-deposition exposure of the hybrid films to the ambient air. Thorough analysis of nanostructure of the hybrid films using RBS, TEM, XRD and Raman spectrometry allowed us to identify the Cu_2O - C_{60} phase composition and to confirm the x -driven tunability of the film nanostructure. The established tunable nanostructure of the hybrid films and some remarkable coincidences in the absorption spectra of C_{60} and Cu_2O allowed us to establish the optical spectrum features suggesting resonant strong coupling between the C_{60} Frenkel exciton

and the Cu₂O Wannier-Mott exciton induced at X-point of Brillouin zone. In particular, careful examination of the Cu_x(O_y)C₆₀ absorption spectra using set of the appropriate Lorentzians allowed us to distinguish the product of the resonant excitonic coupling as two Lorentz peaks situated in vicinity of the resonant excitation energy (nearly 3.5 eV). The coupling energy of the hybrid F-WM exciton estimated as the energy interval between the relevant Lorentz peaks was varied from 390 meV to 610 meV if the Cu content in the hybrid film is increasing from 5.5 to 14.7. The relatively high values of the F-WM exciton coupling energy evaluated in this study ascribed to the mediated effect of nanocavity photons and quantum confinement, that makes it possible to detect the FWM hybrid exciton even at RT. The established correlation between the hybrid film nanostructure (determined by Cu content, x) and the FWM-exciton coupling energy anticipates a remarkable tunability of optical and electronic properties of the self-assembled Cu_x(O_y)C₆₀ hybrid films suggesting bright applications of these materials in optoelectronics and nonlinear optics.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vasily Lavrentiev: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Validation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. **Dagmar Chvostova**: Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - review & editing. **Mariana Klementova**: Investigation, Formal analysis. **Karla Kuldova**: Investigation, Formal analysis. **Esther de Prado**: Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jiri Vacik**: Investigation, Funding acquisition, Writing - review & editing. **Inna Lavrentieva**: Investigation, Formal analysis. **Alexandr Dejneka**: Resources, Methodology, Writing - review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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